

Plan Generation Metrics by Model

Plan Count

Context Complexity

Plan Body Complexity

Novel Goals Count

Novel Beliefs Count

Redundancy Amount

↓ Lower is better

Goal Semantic Misalignment

↓ Lower is better

Belief Semantic Misalignment

↓ Lower is better

Generalization Count

↑ Higher is better

Task Success Rate (%)

↑ Higher is better

